

Quality Criteria

for DMP Templates – Analysis across NFDI

Autors

Celia Krause, Katharina Bergmann, Daniela Hausen, Roman Riedel, Jürgen Windeck

Contributors

Tabea Krause

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1. Introduction and Approach

Data Management Plans (DMPs) are designed to support researchers to plan their data management activities. In the past, a number of DMP templates have been developed by NFDI consortia, Collaborative Research Centres (CRCs), universities and non-university research organisations. The development of specific DMP templates allows tailor-made support for researchers. However, there is a lack of generally accepted quality criteria that can be used during development or to assist in the selection of existing templates.

To address this issue, the Data Management Planning Working Group (infra-dmp), as part of the National Research Data Infrastructure (NFDI) Common Infrastructures section, has analysed various DMP templates and identified quality criteria to be used as guidelines. The target audience for these quality criteria are data stewards and data curators, as well as personnel working in research data management (RDM) infrastructure and consulting. For their suggestions and constructive feedback, we would like to acknowledge the DMP Working Group within the Research Data Working Group of DINI e.V.

For the development of the quality criteria, a generic catalogue of criteria was developed, divided into content and formal criteria. The catalogue was based on the analysis of a large number of existing DMP templates.¹ Technical criteria such as interfaces for dynamic integration of data from other systems, data export functions or automated data synchronisation were not included, as they are purely technical and not template specific.² The basic question for the criteria catalogue was which selection and quality criteria are relevant for the evaluation of templates. By summarising the characteristics of the templates, a first overview of the aspects that are already covered by the DMP templates was obtained in view of the confusing variety of options.

Each criterion was described, classified and evaluated in a table (Chapter 3). In a second step, the collected criteria were refined, classified and divided into five different levels. The result could potentially contribute to a future standard that could serve as a starting point for the development of a template database with filtering capabilities. This would make it easier to identify suitable templates for specific objectives and to develop customised templates with greater fine-tuning.

Tim Berners-Lee's 5-star model for open data visualisation³ served as a template for the visualisation. The criteria were designed to be flexible enough to meet specific needs, but also to provide a 'common denominator' across the NFDI. The result not only promotes a degree of consistency in the creation of DMPs and their templates, but also facilitates their comparability and interchangeability at national level. The final product is easily accessible, easy to use and can be integrated into different application contexts.

¹ See list of examples at the end of the document (Chapter 4).

² Other studies can be cited for technical criteria, cf. <https://ulb-dok.uibk.ac.at/ulbtirolfodok/download/pdf/4406683?originalFilename=true>.

³ Cf. <https://5stardata.info/de/>.

2. Explanation of Quality Levels

The classification of the collected criteria into five levels was based on the estimated level of effort required to implement the criterion in a template, in terms of how resource intensive the implementation of the criterion is for a template. The levels in Figure 1 thus illustrate the level of detail or complexity of a template. The decision as to which criterion is fulfilled by the most templates was not crucial. They indicate how well suited or comprehensive a template is to specific application goals or how much help it can provide. For example, for communication between researchers and research funders, a basic DMP template, which could be classified at levels 1-2, may be perfectly sufficient and therefore qualitatively satisfactory. Templates at higher levels, however, differ significantly from the status of a DMP template and can instead be understood as guidelines on a graduated scale.

In Figure 1, a level 3 dividing line indicates which criteria are essential or relative. Essential core criteria are those that should be included in generic templates (left side). Advanced criteria are considered 'relative', i.e. desirable for a discipline-specific template, but not necessarily essential (right-hand side).

Two of the criteria mentioned are themselves formulated in two levels, Data Quality 1 and 2, and FAIR Data Principles 1 and 2. Each level refers to a different level of competence, with level 1 requiring less and level 2 requiring more in-depth knowledge, research and skills to implement the criterion. Clarifying rights protection is essential in many scientific institutions before making digital reproductions and collected research data accessible. However, implementation and legal assessment can be challenging in individual cases due to the high level of expertise required. Legal issues are already included in the Core Requirements criterion (Level 1) as "legal and ethical requirements". However, in the most demanding Level 5, they are listed separately again, especially when formulating questions about rights protection, etc. for specific disciplinary communities.

Fig. 1 Quality criteria for DMP templates according to the LOD 5-Star model by Tim Berners Lee

Content-related quality criteria: Font without formatting ; formal quality criteria: Italic font

2.1 Listing of Quality Criteria, segregated by Levels

Level 1

- **Core Requirements:** The Science Europe Core Requirements for DMPs are covered in the template.
- **Distinctness:** *The structure is comprehensible and the questions are clearly formulated.*

Level 2

- **General explanations:** Additional content-related explanations, links and notes are provided to further explain the questions.
- **Question cascade:** The questions in the template build upon each other.
- **Process optimisation:** *The template takes into account the typical work processes of a community or an organisation (data management or data curation).*
- **Data quality 1:** Questions are asked about the general inspection of data quality.

Level 3

- **Answer options:** Answer options are offered in the template.
- **FAIR Data Principles 1:** The FAIR principles are taken into account in the questions and are briefly explained in each case.
- **Text modules:** *Formulated text modules are available for answering the questions.*
- **Modules:** *There is a division into a basic module and individual selectable content-related modules.*
- **Institution-specific content:** Institution-specific aspects are included in the template.

Level 4

- **To Do list:** The template supports the development of the DMP by specifying concrete tasks or measures, responsible persons and deadlines.
- **Subject-specific aspects:** Subject-specific or community-specific aspects are included in the template.
- **FAIR Data Principles 2:** Specific instructions are given on the FAIR assessment or the implementation of the FAIR principles in the data.

Level 5

- **Best practices:** In addition to the questions, practical use cases are mentioned or referred to.
- **Data quality 2:** Reference is made to measures/strategies and solutions for checking data quality.
- **Detailed questions on legal aspects:** There is a set of special questions on legal clarification or the clarification of property rights and corresponding explanations.
- **Extensions:** Method-specific, content-related or useful extensions for project planning can be included in the template.

3. Table of Quality Criteria

No.	Criterion	Description / categorisation (What does this criterion mean?)	Examples ⁴ (e.g. from an existing template)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Level 1 •• Level 2 ••• Level 3 •••• Level 4 ••••• Level 5
Content-Related Criteria				
1	Core Requirements The Science Europe Core Requirements for DMPs are covered within the template.	The core requirements contain six topics ⁵ which should be covered in DMP templates, each with several key questions. These topics and questions on the structure of a DMP form the core of a DMP and are also included in the templates of funders. The order can be changed depending on requirements and organisational priorities. Legal aspects are also part of the core requirements and should be an essential component of a DMP.	NFDI4Ing NFDI4Chem Science Europe	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •
2	General explanations Additional content-related explanations, links and notes are provided to further explain the questions.	The questions in the template are supported sufficiently by generic explanations and assistance texts on research data management and, if appropriate, by further information, literature references, training materials and links.	Science Europe RDMO Horizon Europe C3RDM Clarin Wizard	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ••
3	Question cascade The questions in the template build upon each other.	The questions are arranged from general to specific and go into increasing detail.	RDMO Horizon Europe RDMO Katalog Clarin Wizard	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ••
4	Data quality 1 Questions are asked about the general inspection of data quality.	Data quality is explicitly addressed in the DMP in order to introduce users to the topic of ensuring and improving data quality. Data quality is already included in the core requirements (No. 1). However, general questions on this can also be formulated in a separate section - with explanations if necessary.	Science Europe RDMO Katalog RDMO DFG Checkliste NFDI4Chem NFDI4Ing Clarin Wizard	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ••

⁴ The sources of the template examples can be found in chapter 4 at the end of the table.

⁵ 1. Data description and collection or re-use of existing data, 2. Documentation and data quality, 3. Storage and backup during the research process, 4. Legal and ethical requirements, codes of conduct, 5. Data sharing and long-term preservation, 6. Data management responsibilities and resources.

5	<p>FAIR Data Principles 1</p> <p>The FAIR principles are taken into account in the questions and are briefly explained in each case.</p>	<p>Compliance with FAIR ensures good reusability of the data. In order to be able to reuse the data, the FAIR principles are taken into account in the questions and are described briefly. This can be done, for example, as soon as a question touches on a FAIR principle. A reference to FAIR can, for example, encourage users to consider the reusability of their data.</p>	<p>(Science Europe⁶) RDMO Horizon Europe</p>	<p>•••</p>
6	<p>Institution-specific content</p> <p>Institution-specific aspects are included in the template.</p>	<p>The generic template supports adaptation to the specific needs of an institution, e.g. an institution in the GLAM sector or a specialised research institute with a homogeneous work profile. However, such customisation is not always appropriate or necessary.</p>	<p>(JKI-BLE Katalog)</p>	<p>•••</p>
7	<p>To Do list</p> <p>The template supports the development of the DMP by specifying concrete tasks or measures, responsible persons and deadlines.</p>	<p>Specific work steps to achieve certain requirements for research data management and concrete instructions for action are provided as checklists that can be ticked off. It encourages users to continue using, adapting and expanding the DMP for their own project management during the project.</p>	<p>STAMP RDMO Katalog C3RDM</p>	<p>••••</p>
8	<p>Subject-specific aspects</p> <p>Subject-specific or community-specific aspects are included in the template.</p>	<p>The template is customised to a specific subject or sector-specific context. This means that the questions relate solely to the specific needs and usage scenarios of a particular community. This also includes data communities, for example.</p>	<p>NFDI4Chem NFDI4Ing EmiMin STAMP (NFDI4Culture⁷)</p>	<p>••••</p>
9	<p>FAIR Data Principles 2</p> <p>Specific instructions are given on the FAIR assessment or the implementation of the FAIR principles in the data.</p>	<p>Compliance with FAIR ensures good reusability of the data. In order to be able to reuse the data, guidance or instructions for concrete steps to implement the different FAIR principles are provided and made verifiable, e.g. in the form of a FAIR check module.</p>	<p>—</p>	<p>••••</p>

⁶ The FAIR principles are not specifically addressed (by means of an explanation), even if they are implicitly considered in individual questions.

⁷ Currently in planning.

10	<p>Best practices</p> <p>In addition to the questions, practical use cases are mentioned or referred to.</p>	Case studies or practical use cases from a subject community are presented to supplement the questions and help to promote a practical understanding of the question catalogue. Where possible, this should be done by referring to another resource in order to keep the DMP light.	NFDI4Ing STAMP NFDI4Chem	•••••
11	<p>Data quality 2</p> <p>Reference is made to measures/strategies and solutions for checking data quality.</p>	Special methods for ensuring data quality are presented in a practical way and a guide is provided for checking data quality or for implementing quality assurance and improvement (via tool connection or reference). If necessary, a link to quality management is made possible.	—	•••••
12	<p>Detailed questions on legal aspects</p> <p>There is a set of special questions on legal clarification or the clarification of property rights and corresponding explanations.⁸</p>	Protective rights include data protection (DSGVO, handling of sensitive data, anonymisation of persons), copyright (texts, images, audio-visual material, ...), domiciliary rights (freedom of panorama), etc.	RDMO Katalog Science Europe RDMO Horizon Europe STAMP ...	•••••
13	<p>Extensions</p> <p>Method-specific, content-related or useful extensions for project planning can be included in the template.</p>	The components of the extensions can either be added as separate modules or are available as individual templates. ⁹ They can actively support the research data management.	MaRDMO, EmiMin (RDMO4Life) STAMP	•••••
Formal Criteria				
1	<p>Distinctness</p> <p>The structure is comprehensible and the questions are formulated precisely.</p>	The catalogue of questions is clearly structured and the order of the questions/items is transparent. The questions are distinct, i.e. there is no content overlap between questions or redundancy.	HeFDI Clarín Wizard	•

⁸ See <https://www.berd-nfdi.de/servicetools/legal-questions-in-data-science/>.

⁹ Such extensions could be: Templates for quantity structures (collections), mapping of workflows/processes (projects, infrastructure institutions). The following are also thinkable: Mapping of points for data transfer, cataloguing and publication concepts (projects, collections), management strategies (projects, infrastructure facilities), responsibilities and roles (projects, infrastructure facilities), decision trees/aids, etc.

2	<p>Process optimisation</p> <p>The template takes into account the typical work processes of a community or an organisation. (data management or data curation)</p>	<p>The order of the question catalogue is designed to facilitate continuous updating, e.g. based on the data life cycle in relation to the work processes within an institution: planning, collection, processing/enrichment, (evaluation), backup, storage, publication/sharing, subsequent use. This also includes, for example, a segmentation according to data type or data category.</p>	—	••
3	<p>Answer options</p> <p>Answer options are offered in the template.</p>	<p>Answer options can be displayed as bullet points or directly as tick-off boxes (checkboxes). In contrast to text modules (No. 4), however, these are not longer continuous texts. They support the quick completion of the DMP and make it easier to get started. They also enable automated evaluation of the template after processing (keyword: maDMP).</p>	<p>NFDI4Ing RDMO DFG- Checkliste HeFDI NFDI4Chem Clarín Wizard</p>	•••
4	<p>Text modules</p> <p>Formulated text modules are available for answering the questions.</p>	<p>In particular cases (questions on long-term archiving, intellectual property rights, etc.) specific text modules can be formulated for answering the questions. There may be several texts to choose from. Such text modules¹⁰ support the quick completion of the DMP and make it easier to get started. However, they are not appropriate or necessary in every case (therefore in the area of relative criteria) and, in contrast to the answer options (No. 3), can be expanded as required.</p>	<p>Horizon 2020 Clarín Wizard RDMO Horizon Europe</p>	•••

¹⁰ e.g. 'The dataset is published via the N.N. repository. The repository automatically assigns a DOI to each dataset and guarantees that the dataset can be accessed via DOI, even if it has been moved to a new URL. If the dataset itself cannot yet be made accessible, for example because data protection issues have not yet been conclusively clarified, the documentation of the dataset is published in parallel via the repository. This means that the metadata and, if applicable, the access conditions are freely and permanently available. This ensures that the dataset is easy to identify and can be permanently cited and referenced at any time.'

5	<p>Modules</p> <p>There is a division into a basic module and individual selectable content-related modules.</p>	<p>In addition to information on the project and funders, the catalogue of questions in the basic module also includes the option of entering information on the gathered data and material. Depending on requirements, modules on content-related aspects can be added in a modular fashion, e.g. rights management, data organisation, documentation, LTA, etc.</p>	STAMP	...
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4. List of Example Catalogues

C3RDM Template: https://fdm.uni-koeln.de/sites/FDM-UzK/Templates/DMP_UzK_20180201.docx

Clarín Wizard: <https://www.clarin-d.net/de/aufbereiten/datenmanagementplan-entwickeln>

EmiMin: <https://github.com/rdmorganiser/rdmo-catalog/tree/master/shared/EmiMin>

HeFDI: <https://github.com/rdmorganiser/rdmo-catalog/tree/master/shared/HeFDI>

JKI BLE Katalog: https://github.com/rdmorganiser/rdmo-catalog/tree/master/shared/BLE_JKI

NFDI4Chem:

Hausen, D. A., & Andres, A.-C. (2024). Chemistry-specific Data Management Plan Template based on DFG checklist. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10948510>

NFDI4Ing: https://github.com/rdmorganiser/rdmo-catalog/tree/master/shared/nfdi4ing/NFDI4Ing_template

MaRDMO Questionnaire: <https://github.com/MarcoReidelbach/MaRDMO-Questionnaire>

RDMO DFG-Checkliste: <https://github.com/rdmorganiser/rdmo-catalog/blob/master/rdmorganiser/questions/DFG-Checkliste.xml>

RDMO Horizon Europe: <https://github.com/rdmorganiser/rdmo-catalog/blob/master/rdmorganiser/questions/horizon-europe.xml>

RDMO Katalog: <https://github.com/rdmorganiser/rdmo-catalog/blob/master/rdmorganiser/questions/rdmo.xml>

Science Europe: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4915861>

STAMP: <https://www.forschungsdaten-bildung.de/stamp-nutzen>